

CYLINDRICAL BENDING OF ANISOTROPIC LAMINATED PLATES INCLUDING THE EFFECT OF TRANSVERSE SHEAR AND NORMAL STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of anisotropy, shear deformation, and transverse normal stress on the cylindrical bending of laminated, anisotropic plates subjected to a uniform lateral load is investigated. Field equations are based on Reissner's principle in a modified form which requires assumed interlaminar shear and normal stress distributions in addition to the inplane displacements. Numerical results from closed form solutions are compared for laminates with clamped, simply-supported, and cantilever type boundary conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

A laminated plate theory has been developed for the bending of laminated, anisotropic plates which includes the effects of both transverse shear deformation and transverse normal stress without increasing the number of bending equations above those generated in classical shear deformation theory [1]. The midplane strains, however, do not vanish requiring solution to an inplane problem in order to completely describe plate behavior. Resulting field equations are based on Reissner's principle in a modified form which requires assumed interlaminar shear and normal stress distributions in addition to the inplane displacements. Numerical results for cylindrical bending of laminated, anisotropic plates subjected to a half sine wave lateral load showed that improved results for bending deflections can be obtained by including transverse normal stress effects as well as transverse shear deformation effects. These numerical results were obtained for simply-supported boundary conditions and results compared to exact solutions from classical theory of elasticity. This work has been extended to the case of cylindrical bending of simply-supported laminated plates under uniform transverse load [2].

In this paper the previous work in conjunction with uniformly loaded anisotropic plates subjected to cylindrical bending is extended to the case of cantilever type boundary conditions. The effect of anisotropy, transverse shear deformation, and transverse normal strain is assessed by comparing solutions for two laminate geometries in conjunction with clamped, simply-supported, and the current cantilever type boundary conditions.

2. CYLINDRICAL BENDING

Consider a rectangular laminated plate of thickness h with a symmetric stacking sequence relative to the plate midplane. Each ply is constructed of an orthotropic material with the principle axis of orthotropy oriented at an arbitrary angle, θ , relative to the x -axis of the plate. The inplane displacements are assumed to be of the form

$$u = u^0(x, y) + z \psi_x(x, y), \quad v = v^0(x, y) + z \psi_y(x, y) \quad (1)$$

while the plate deflection, w , is expressed in terms of the weighted displacement [1]

$$w^* = \frac{3}{2h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} w(x, y, z) \left[1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right] dz \quad (2)$$

The ply constitutive equations are of the form

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ik} \epsilon_k + \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} \sigma_3 \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 6) \quad (3)$$

where σ_i , ϵ_i , C_{ik} , and Q_{ij} are the stresses, strains, stiffnesses, and reduced stiffnesses, respectively.

The constitutive relations in terms of inplane force resultants and moments are given by [1]

$$\begin{aligned} N_i &= A_{ij} \epsilon_j + L_i (p_1 + p_2) \\ M_i &= D_{ij} \kappa_j + J_i (p_1 - p_2) \end{aligned} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (4)$$

where

$$(N_i, M_i) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_i(1, z) dz, \quad (A_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij}(1, z^2) dz$$

$$L_i = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} dz, \quad J_i = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{C_{i3}}{C_{33}} \left(\frac{z}{h}\right) \left[3 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right] z dz$$

$$p_1 = \sigma_3(h/2), \quad p_2 = \sigma_3(-h/2)$$

We note in Equation 4 that the inplane force resultants are coupled to the lateral surface tractions. Thus, the midplane strains do not vanish in the case of the bending due to lateral load when the effects of transverse normal stress are considered. Reissner did not consider midplane strains in the development of his theory for homogeneous, isotropic plates [3]. We now change to the conventional nomenclature in which the subscripts 1, 2, and 3 denote, x, y, and z, respectively, while 6 corresponds to ψ .

The constitutive relations for the transverse shear force resultants, Q_x and Q_y are given by [1]

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_x \\ Q_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{55} & F_{45} \\ F_{45} & F_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_x + w^*_{,x} \\ \psi_y + w^*_{,y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where

$$F_{44} = \frac{R_{55}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}, \quad F_{55} = \frac{R_{44}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}, \quad F_{45} = -\frac{R_{45}}{(R_{44} R_{55} - R_{45}^2)}$$

and

$$R_{ij} = \frac{9}{4h^2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} S_{ij} \left[1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2\right]^2 dz \quad (i, j = 4, 5)$$

Here S_{ij} denotes the anisotropic transverse shear compliances. The transverse shear resultants are defined in the usual manner, i.e.

$$(Q_x, Q_y) = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}) dz \tag{6}$$

where τ_{ij} denotes shear stress relative to the i - j plane. These constitutive relations are developed with the assumption that the interlaminar stresses are of the same form as utilized by Reissner [3] for homogeneous, isotropic plates, namely

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xz} &= [1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2] \frac{3Q_x}{2h} \\ \tau_{yz} &= [1 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2] \frac{3Q_y}{2h} \\ \sigma_z &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ [3 - 4 \left(\frac{z}{h}\right)^2] \left(\frac{z}{h}\right) (p_1 - p_2) + (p_1 + p_2) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

For cylindrical bending we consider a symmetric laminate where the length in the y -direction is much longer than the x -direction, as illustrated in Fig. 1. If the laminate is subjected to a lateral load

Figure 1. Cylindrical Bending

which is independent of y , then the resulting deformations will be independent of y . Such cases are referred to as cylindrical bending. The displacements in eq. (1) and (2) now take the form

$$u^0 = U(x), v^0 = V(x), \psi_x = \Psi'_x(x), \psi_y = \Psi'_y(x), w^* = W(x) \tag{8}$$

Denoting differentiation with respect to x by a prime, the inplane equilibrium equations reduce to the following [1]

$$N_x' = 0, N_{xy}' = 0 \tag{9}$$

which leads to constant values of N_x and N_{xy} . For the case of symmetric laminates the bending equations are of the form [1]

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} \Psi_x'' - F_{55} \Psi_x + D_{16} \Psi_y'' - F_{45} \Psi_y - F_{55} W' + J_1 (p_1' - p_2') &= 0 \\ D_{16} \Psi_x'' - F_{45} \Psi_x + D_{66} \Psi_y'' - F_{44} \Psi_y - F_{45} W' + J_6 (p_1' - p_2') &= 0 \\ F_{55} \Psi_x' + F_{45} \Psi_y' + F_{55} W'' + (p_1 - p_2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The homogeneous solution to Equations (10) are given by the following relationships

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{xh} &= c_1 + c_2 x + \frac{c_3}{2} x^2 - \frac{D_{16}}{D_{11}} (A \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{a} + B \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{a}) \\ \Psi_{yh} &= c_3 H_1 + A \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{a} + B \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{a} \\ W_h &= c_4 - c_1 x - \frac{c_2}{2} x^2 + \frac{c_3}{6} (6H_2 - x^2) x + \frac{hH_3}{\lambda} (A \sinh \lambda \frac{x}{a} + B \cosh \lambda \frac{x}{a}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where the subscript h denotes the homogeneous solution and

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= \frac{a}{h} \sqrt{\frac{(F_{44}F_{55} - F_{45}^2)D_{11}h^2}{F_{55}(D_{11}D_{66} - D_{16}^2)}}, \quad H_1 = \frac{(F_{55}D_{16} - F_{45}D_{11})}{(F_{44}F_{55} - F_{45}^2)} \\ H_2 &= \frac{(F_{44}D_{11} - F_{45}D_{16})}{(F_{44}F_{55} - F_{45}^2)}, \quad H_3 = \frac{(F_{55}D_{16} - F_{45}D_{11})}{F_{55}D_{11}} \end{aligned}$$

Obviously the particular solution depends on the form of the lateral loading. We will now consider a uniform pressure.

3. UNIFORM LOAD

For a uniform lateral load

$$p_1 = p_0 = \text{constant}, \quad p_2 = 0 \quad (12)$$

Because the lateral load is constant, the effect of transverse normal stress vanishes from the first two relationships in Equations 11 with the result

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11} \Psi_x'' - F_{55} \Psi_x + D_{16} \Psi_y'' - F_{45} \Psi_y - F_{55} W' &= 0 \\ D_{16} \Psi_x'' - F_{45} \Psi_x + D_{66} \Psi_y'' - F_{44} \Psi_y - F_{45} W' &= 0 \\ F_{55} \Psi_x' + F_{45} \Psi_y' + F_{55} W'' + p_0 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

A particular solution to Equations 14 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{xp} &= -\frac{p_0}{6D_{11}} x^3, \quad \Psi_{yp} = -\frac{H_1}{D_{11}} p_0 x \\ W_p &= - (12H_2 - x^2) \frac{p_0}{24D_{11}} x^2 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the subscript p denotes the particular solution.

The width of the plate is denoted by a and the axis system is placed at the center of the width such that

$-a/2 \leq x \leq a/2$ (see Figure 1). At the laminate level, transverse normal stress will only effect cases in which force and/or moment boundary conditions are required. In particular, because transverse normal stress effects do not appear in Equations (13), they enter the problem through force and/or moment boundary conditions, as observed in the constitutive relations, Equations (4). Thus, for example, in the case of clamped boundaries, which involves displacement conditions only, transverse normal stress effects will not be present at the laminate level. Transverse normal stress will, however, have an effect on the ply stresses by virtue of Equation (3).

3.1 Clamped and Simply-Supported Boundary Conditions

For clamped boundaries at $x = \pm a/2$

$$U = V = \Psi_x = \Psi_y = W = 0 \quad (15)$$

and for simply-supported boundaries we require that at $x = \pm a/2$

$$N_x = N_{xy} = W = M_x = M_{xy} = 0 \quad (16)$$

The results for these two boundary conditions have been previously presented in References 2 and 4, respectively. The maximum deflection in each of these cases is of the form

$$w^*_{\max} = W(0) = w_{\text{CLPT}} (1 + H) \quad (17)$$

where w_{CLPT} is the solution as obtained from classical laminated plate theory. For clamped boundaries

$$w_{\text{CLPT}} = \frac{a^4}{384D_{11}} p_0 \quad (18)$$

$$H = \frac{48}{a^2} \left\{ \frac{D_{11}}{F_{55}} + H_1 H_3 \left[1 - \frac{4}{\lambda^2} \left(\frac{\cosh \frac{\lambda}{2} - 1}{\sinh \frac{\lambda}{2}} \right) \right] \right\}$$

and for simply-supported boundaries

$$w_{\text{CLPT}} = \frac{5a^4}{384D_{11}} p_0 \quad (19)$$

$$H = \frac{48}{5a^2} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{F_{55}} - J_1 + H_1 H_3 \left(1 - \frac{8}{\lambda^2} \right) + \frac{8H_3 D_{11}}{\lambda^2} \left(\frac{J_6 D_{11} - J_1 D_{16}}{D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2} \right) \left(\frac{\cosh \frac{\lambda}{2} - 1}{\sinh \frac{\lambda}{2}} \right) \right]$$

3.2 Cantilever Plate

We now consider the case of a cantilever type loading as shown in Figure 2. Note that for convenience we take the origin of the coordinate system at the clamped end of the cantilever rather than at the center of the width as in the case of clamped and simply-supported edges. The boundary conditions are of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_x(0) = \Psi_y(0) = W(0) = M_x(a) = M_{xy}(a) = Q_x(a) = 0 \\ u^0(0) = v^0(0) = N_x(a) = N_{xy}(a) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The 6 boundary conditions in the first of Equations 20 will allow the 6 coefficients c_i , A, and B to be obtained. If we wish to determine U and V, then we use the second of Equations 20 in conjunction with the equilibrium condition, Equation 9, which leads to $N_x = N_{xy} = 0$ throughout the plate. The inplane displacements can then be determined from the first of the constitutive relations in Equations 4.

Figure 2. Cantilever plate under uniform lateral load.

The resulting solution for the maximum deflection, w^*_{max} , is of the same form as Equation 17 for clamped and simply-supported boundary conditions with

$$w_{CLPT} = \frac{a^4}{8D_{11}} p_0$$

$$H = \frac{4}{a^2} \left\{ \frac{D_{11}}{F_{55}} + J_1 + H_1 H_3 \left[1 + \frac{2}{\lambda^2} \frac{(\cosh \lambda - \lambda \sinh \lambda + 1)}{\cosh \lambda} \right] \right. \quad (21)$$

$$\left. - \frac{2H_3 D_{11}}{\lambda^2} \frac{(J_1 D_{11} - J_6 D_{16}) (\cosh \lambda - 1)}{D_{11} D_{66} - D_{16}^2} \right\}$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We now consider laminates with the following unidirectional ply properties

$$\begin{aligned} E_L/E_T = 16, \quad G_{LT}/E_T = G_{L3}/E_T = 0.615, \quad G_{T3}/E_T = 0.323, \\ \nu_{LT} = \nu_{L3} = 0.3, \quad \nu_{T3} = 0.55 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where the subscript L, T, and 3 denote axes parallel to the fiber, perpendicular to the fiber, and through-the-thickness of a unidirectional composite, respectively. In addition E_i , G_{ij} , and ν_{ij} denote the Young's modulus in the i th direction, the shear modulus relative to the i - j plane, and the Poisson's ratio measured by contraction in the j th direction during a uniaxial tensile test in the i th direction, respectively. These properties represent state-of-the-art unidirectional graphite/epoxy composites.

Numerical results are shown in Tables 1-3 for the maximum deflection normalized by w_{CLPT} for $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ_2]_S$ and $[0^\circ_2/\pm 45^\circ]_S$ laminates. In this context

$$W = \frac{w_{\max}^*}{w_{\text{CLPT}}} \quad (23)$$

In these tables the subscript AN denotes the anisotropic theory with both shear deformation and normal stress effects included, while AS denotes the anisotropic solution with shear deformation only. The effect of anisotropy is also investigated by obtaining orthotropic solutions in which coupling terms are neglected ($F_{45}, D_{16}, D_{26} = 0$). In particular, OS denotes the orthotropic solution with shear deformation and ON denotes the orthotropic solution with both shear deformation and transverse normal stress effects included.

Table 1. Maximum deflection for clamped boundaries.
 $w_{\max}^*/w_{\text{CLPT}}$

a/h	[±45°/0° ₂] _S		[0° ₂ /±45°] _S	
	w _{AS}	w _{OS}	w _{AS}	w _{OS}
5	3.335	3.188	7.243	7.241
10	1.584	1.547	2.561	2.560
20	1.146	1.137	1.390	1.390
30	1.065	1.061	1.173	1.173

Table 2. Maximum deflection for simply-supported boundaries.
 $w_{\max}^*/w_{\text{CLPT}}$

a/h	w _{AN}	w _{AS}	w _{ON}	w _{OS}
[±45°/0° ₂] _S				
5	1.293	1.467	1.264	1.438
10	1.073	1.117	1.006	1.109
20	1.018	1.029	1.016	1.027
30	1.008	1.013	1.007	1.012
[0° ₂ /±45°] _S				
5	1.981	2.249	1.981	2.248
10	1.245	1.312	1.245	1.312
20	1.061	1.078	1.061	1.078
30	1.027	1.035	1.027	1.035

Table 3. Maximum deflection for cantilever plate.
 w_{max}^*/w_{CLPT}

a/h	w_{AN}	w_{AS}	w_{ON}	w_{OS}
$[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ_2]_S$				
5	1.273	1.202	1.255	1.182
10	1.069	1.051	1.064	1.046
20	1.017	1.013	1.016	1.011
30	1.008	1.006	1.007	1.005
$[0^\circ_2/\pm 45^\circ]_S$				
5	1.634	1.522	1.632	1.520
10	1.158	1.131	1.158	1.130
20	1.040	1.033	1.039	1.033
30	1.018	1.015	1.018	1.014

5. DISCUSSION

A cursory examination of Tables 1-3 reveals that the effect of anisotropy is small for the laminates under consideration with, obviously, the largest effect being for the $[\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ_2]_S$ laminates. Inclusion of transverse shear deformation is more significant than transverse normal stress. As one would anticipate the effect of transverse shear deformation depends on the boundary conditions with clamped boundaries providing the most severe case and cantilever type boundaries the least severe case. Transverse normal stress effects are significant at low width-to-thickness ratios. Inclusion of transverse normal stress reduces the maximum deflection compared to shear deformation for simply-supported boundaries. This is consistent with the results presented by Whitney and Rose [1] where comparison with exact elasticity solutions showed that shear deformation alone overestimated the maximum deflection. The inclusion of both shear deformation and transverse normal stress, in the same manner as presented here, gave almost identical results to exact elasticity. For the cantilever plate, however, the inclusion of transverse normal stress increased the maximum deflection.

References

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